

FIRST RECORD OF GARLIC MOTH *DYSPESSA ULULA* (LEPIDOPTERA: COSSIDAE) IN *ALLIUM SATIVUM* CULTIVATION IN THE PELOPONNESE AREA (GREECE)

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Mantzoukas, S. & Karanastasi, E. First record of garlic moth *Dyspessa ulula* (Lepidoptera: Cossidae) at *Allium sativum* cultivation in the Peloponnese area (Greece). Summary. Garlic moth *Dyspessa ulula* (Borkhausen, 1790) detected in an experimental cultivation in the prefecture of Iliia, Western Greece is recorded for the first time in this part of the country.

Key words: Cossidae, garlic moth, *Dyspessa ulula*, *Allium sativum*, Iliia, Greece.

Манцукас, С. і Каранастазі, Е. Перша знахідка часникової червиці *Dyspessa ulula* (Lepidoptera: Cossidae) на полях *Allium sativum* в районі Пелопоннеса (Греція). Резюме. Часникова червиця (Borkhausen, 1790) знайдена на експериментальних полях у префектурі Ілія, Західна Греція, вперше зареєстрована у цій частині країни.

Ключові слова: Cossidae, часникова червиця, *Dyspessa ulula*, *Allium sativum*, Ілія, Греція.

Introduction

In the recent years, the cultivation of garlic in Greece shows a tendency to increase. In 2017, garlic cultivation spread over 1250 hectares with a total production volume of 9,700 tons. It is very important to make a 3–4 year crop-rotation and to avoid planting garlic in the same plot that had previously been used for root vegetables, because bulb infections and stem nematodes can also damage it. Moreover, other *Allium* species should not be planted in the same plot that had previously been used for garlic because of the risk from same pests and diseases (Beshkov, 2017). The garlic moth, *Dyspessa ulula* (Borkhausen, 1790), larvae, which enter the plant from the soil, damage the interior of the bulb by creating caverns. In Coustis & Ghavalas (2001) as well as in Hacker (1989); Stojanovic & Curcic (2011) and Beshkov & Nahirnic (2016), no geographical zones were specified for this moth in Greece. This experimental cultivation was aimed to detect the presence of garlic moth in Iliia, Western Greece.

Material and Methods

The material was collected in experimental garlic fields in Iliia from the mid-May to the end of July. Larvae were obtained from infested garlic bulbs and the moths were collected at the Osram 160W mixed light and a black light bulb with a generator (Yakolvev, 2004; 2005; 2006; Saldaitis, Yakolvev & Ivinskis, 2007). Plants were examined for garlic moth larvae infection (*D. ulula*) twice per year. The genitalia slides studied using MBI-3 stereoscope and images were taken with a Nikon D-90 camera.

Results and discussion

The symptoms appear when larvae start developing within the bulb of the garlic. Some outer layers of affected garlic bulbs have yellow-brownish coloring (Fig. 1a). Garlic bulbs with signs of brownish dry rot, may be

Figs 1–3. Garlic moth larvae: 1 — Infected garlic head with larvae; 2 — third instar larvae; 3 — second instar pink larvae.

totally or partially tunneled and consist of froth mass with caterpillar feces (Fig. 1b). In infected garlic bulbs, we found all the larval stages (Beshkov & Wenger, 2004). This is the first record of *D. ulula* in the Peloponnese area. The identification of the species was based on infested garlic bulb samples, which were originally collected from an experimental cultivation in Ilia and were maintained at $25\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ for observation. Based on the adult and larval morphological characteristics, the species was identified as the *D. ulula*, or Garlic Moth (Lepidoptera: Cossidae) (Tolman, 2003). Their colouring is pink. The head is black. Pink color extends along the dorsal and the lateral sides. The ventral parts of the larvae are pale. (Fig. 2). Natural enemies of *Dyspessa ulula* and their biological cycle have not yet been recorded in the Peloponnese area across Greece. Therefore, it is important to initiate a monitoring program to identify and record natural enemies (predators, parasitoids, entomopathogens) and their biological cycle, that could be used as potential biocontrol agents against this important pest of garlic.

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